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CONSEQUENCES OF SOCIAL CONFLICT ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONTEMPORARY NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria has become a centre of frequent violent social conflict since the unholy marriage of different nations. The study did an enquiry of the consequences of social conflict on sustainable development of the contemporary Nigeria. It adopted multicausal theory as its theoretical framework. This study is historical in nature which exclusively relied on secondary sources of data. The work found ethnic identity, economic motivation, relative deprivation, incompetent governance and diversionary use of force among others as causes of social conflict in Nigeria. Political instability, disruption of education programme, threat to national security, proliferation of small arms and light weapons and backward movement were identified as effects of social conflict in Nigeria. The paper concluded that the problem of social conflict in Nigeria is multifaceted putting question of security and survival on the center stage. The study recommended positive construe of plurality and ethnicity, strengthen of social welfare policies, enshrinement of doctrine of social justice, and good governance. Prioritisation of peace response to agitation is also fundamental.

KEYWORDS: Conflict, Pluralistic, Social Conflict, Social Justice, Sustainable Development

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is the most populous African country with over 226 million people of various ethnic groups, a pluralized democracy, a multilingual and multi religious culture with well-recorgnised diversity (Adedeji, 2024). Nigeria is majorly recorgnised to as the giant of Africa and one of Africa's prides, recognized as the world's oldest and second

largest continent and the epicentre of human civilization (Egobueze, 2019).

Nigeria is one of the African countries in the world with abundant potential of becoming great among the committee of nations. It is a power to reckon with, through its participation in international affairs.

Consequently, it has actively involved in management of conflict at sub-regional, regional and international levels with high percentage of success recorded with its human and material resources (Adedeji, 2022).

Ironically, Nigeria has been experiencing severe episodes of different forms of conflict turned violent, and crisis have bedevilled it since independence (Izundu, 2024). The constant conflicts have adversely affected its sustainable development. The recent happening has revealed that the country is immersed in dangerous social conflicts that have open the nation to various insecurity, resulting in a volatile society.

Majority of these social conflicts have their roots in the historical incident and character of Nigeria. Several studies have examined the impact of broader conflict on economy, causal relationship between growth and conflict, impact of conflict on human security, influence of conflict on politics and election. However, very few works have been done on social conflict and sustainable development.

This study therefore intends to address this identified gap by narrowing our study to social conflict and sustainable development of Nigeria. The objective of the study was to interrogate the consequences of social conflict on sustainable development of the contemporary Nigeria in 21st century. In view of this, the paper addresses four questions:

- 1) What are the relationships between social conflict and sustainable development?
- 2) What are the causes of social conflict in Nigeria?

- 3) What are the consequences of social conflict on sustainable development of the 21st century Nigeria?
- 4) What is the central message of social justice in management of social conflict in Nigeria?

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Conflict is an unavoidable aspect of any society. Its interpretation in different ways was prompted by the certainty that conflict would arise. Some of the definitions, however, follow a line of reasoning that explicitly characterizes conflict as an opposition, a condition of incompatibility, a bad portent, and a positive or constructive conclusion (Alimba, 2014). Incompatibility leads to conflict since it is a psychological state in which people disagreeing as conflict could arise when emotions permeate behaviour and manifest in an adversarial manner.

According to Patzak (2012), conflict is an opposition that arises from disagreements with or among persons, groups, units, or societies regarding goals, ideas, or feelings. The main aim of opposition is to prevent a person or group from achieving particular goals, which will cause conflict since the party being prevented will react in a confrontational manner. Conflict, according to Wilmot and Hocker (2011) is a felt wrestle between two or more autonomous people or groups over alleged incompatibilities in their values, beliefs, and objectives, or in their demands for control, connection, and respect.

Conflict can also be defined in terms of positive or negative outcome. It is functional when the outcome is positive, while it is

dysfunctional when it ends up in negative outcomes. According to Hoelscher and Robert (2002), conflict is a phenomenon with fundamental power that can lead to beneficial outcomes by bringing in diverse viewpoints that encourage creative problem-solving. Conflict in its negative form is something that evokes bad feelings, has a negative connotation, and frequently results in devastation (Paradis, Carron, and Martin, 2014).

The perspectives and management styles of the disputing parties determine how a conflict scenario turns out (Adedeji, 2021). In line with the discussion above, conflict arises naturally when people or groups have different needs, values, or objectives. As Adedeji (2021) correctly pointed out, when conflict arises, its expressions and results differ based on the perspectives of the disputing parties and the management strategies utilized.

There are series of definition of social conflict from various scholars. Oberscall (1978) referenced in (Albert, 2012) sees social dispute as one in which the parties are not a single person but rather an assembly of people, such as communities, organizations, and groups. Social conflict can also be viewed as a contention over values or claims to status, authority, and limited resources, where the groups' goals are to neutralize, harm, or eradicate opponents in addition to achieving the desired ideals (Coser, 1967 cited in Albert, 2012).

Coser (2000) went on to describe social conflict as the conflict between reality and ideals that align with the beliefs of specific social groupings or people. Protests, riots,

strikes, intercommunal conflicts, and government actions against the populace that are incited by the public and the public's response to government activities are all considered forms of social conflict (Charland, 2014). Further, social conflict is different from all other forms of conflict with some common indices such as:

- Social conflict put groups as the actor or conflicting party as against individual;
- It has to do with competition for agency or power in a society which includes competition between or among classes, races, ethnicities, religions, genders, generations, etc.;
- It involves needs and interests and mostly caused by scarce resources; and
- It is not limited to physical problems but intellectual engagements such as debating, negotiating, battering, adjudicating, appealing, accommodating, or benefiting

All over the world, nations experience all forms of social conflicts from time immemorial, the study highlighted the following as conspicuous types of social conflicts experienced in Nigeria.

- **Religious conflict:** a type of conflict that manifests when one religious affiliation in attempt to spread is working against the interest of the other. Omotosho (2003) identified the possible causes of religion conflicts to be lack of acknowledgment of one another; promotion of animosity and intimidation, insincerity in appreciating each other's faith and culture; and fanaticism.

- **Communal Conflict:** Its identity is rather fluid in nature and can occur in different forms and sometimes deceptive to identify. Albert (2001) contended that communal conflict often manifest in form of host/stranger dichotomy or citizen/settler conflict. It can also be infused in issue of religion, land, politics, and resources.
- **Political Conflict:** is any conflict based or influenced by or stemming from partisan interest or political ideology. It could be between the citizens and the government; between one political party and another on the issue of electioneering which is called inter-party squabble. It could as well be within a political party which is called intra-party squabble.
- **Labour conflict:** usually occurs between workers' union (labour union) and the authority of government as a result of dissatisfaction on terms of work.
- **Environmental conflict:** is a conflict that arises as a result of degrading environmental resources and increase in the population. This could as well manifest when the available resources are misused to satisfy self-interest of few groups or community at the detriment of the other. The relative deprivation of Niger Delta by Federal Government and the reprisal and militant activities as indication to this deprivation is a good example.

From a conceptual standpoint, social conflict is the zenith of incongruities in relationships between people, groups of people, or the social environment at large. Opposing

interests, goals, and positions of the subjects of interaction are what define it. Whether the conflicts are hidden or obvious, there is always the absence of compromise or even dialogue between and among the parties (Petukhov, 2015).

Sustainable development refers to the efforts made to improve the socioeconomic and ecological status as well as the exploitation and processing of the environment or natural resources in order to advance the value of human life without endangering the needs of future generations. The World Conservation Union popularized the idea of sustainable development in the 20th century with its "World Conservation Strategy."

The Bruntland Commission's report, which was tasked by the UN General Assembly to suggest enduring environmental plans for attaining sustainable development by the year 2000 and beyond, gave the concept increased prominence and attention (Sulaiman, 2002). The report spelled out the concept of sustainable development, its nature, scope, objectives, and approaches, among others.

In line with the majority of definitions, development is a process of altering social structure, attitudes, institutions, and the overall acceleration of economic growth through the reduction in poverty and inequality. Mohammed (2002) further pinpointed three key characteristics through the review of the concept, specifically:

- Expanding the distribution and accessibility of necessities for survival, like food, housing, and safety;
- Raising the standard of living in addition to increasing income, creating

jobs, improving education, and paying more attention to cultural and humanitarian values, all of which contribute to material well-being and boost national and individual self-esteem; and

- Giving people and nations more economic and social options by releasing them from enslavement and reliance.

From the aforementioned, some indicators of development, which are no doubt necessary to sustainable growth, are identified. Adedeji (1997) asserts that the Human Development Index (HDI), which is composed of three components of income, education, and health can be used to gauge the degree of human development. The Gross Domestic Product, which is the overall output of the economy, is a major factor of progress (Aliyu, 1999).

Mohammed (2002) also identified other indicators of development, such as increased life expectancy, which is primarily impacted by the standard of living, accessibility to health care, literacy, and income of the populace, and improved nutritional standards, the availability of decent housing, and high-quality health care and education services for the majority.

Common, definite, acquirable, and possessive resources are the four general categories into which Dogarawa (2002) divided resources. According to him, resources that are shared by all nations, people, and tribes and that no one can stop anyone from using are known as common resources, which include, but are not limited to air, sunlight, moonlight, rain, weather, forests, wild creatures, and time.

Finite resources have terminal characteristics, which is why they must be used quickly, effectively, and efficiently, this includes strategy, completion, objective, and lifespan. In order to transition from one status to another, attainable resources are obtained; skills, experiences, and orientation are a few examples. Customary rights and other legal forms of ownership are used to acquire possessive resources, which can then be used, neglected, sold, or given away as gifts or control.

Possessive resources constitute development ingredients, and their efficient use is largely what ensures sustainability; their underuse or misuse could result in significant loss and disaster. Some examples are money, assets, technology, territory, and independence. The key argument is that in a crisis-ridden environment, it would be difficult to achieve all of the identified development indices, only pseudo-development could be achieved.

Unquestionably, a country cannot be considered politically stable if it experiences crises nearly every week (Ajimotikun 2003). The nation would have been proud of the hundreds of military and civilian lives lost as a result of ceaseless social unrest. It is nevertheless true that unstable governments, which are essential to sustainable development, are bred by crises.

• **Theoretical Framework**

Developing a theory that explains social conflicts in Nigeria is to gain a better understanding of the causes of these social conflicts. The study adopted the multicausal theory as a suitable analytical method to examine the effects of social conflict in

Nigeria. It implies that social conflict in Nigeria is as a result of numerous factors. Consequently, the causation element of this model indicates the necessity of determining the probable causes of communal conflict from a variety of angles.

This further supports the idea that Nigeria contains intrinsic social conflict aspects, which may be structural, political, cultural, religious, geographical and sociological among other variables. The problem of social conflict in Nigeria is multifaceted which has put question of security along with survival of Nigeria on the center stage (Ujomu, 2002). Since independence, the problem of social conflicts in Nigeria have centered on the experiences of the numerous individuals and groups who have faced with social injustice inform of oppression, marginalisation, deprivation, etc.

The above factors have adversely contributed to the erosion of social justice in the Nigerian nation, and therefore institutionalisation of social conflicts in the country (Committee on Defence of Human Rights, 2000a). The multicausal theory is thought to be suitable for identifying probable components of social conflict and elucidating how these components may interact to weaken peace in the nation. The theory enables a more thorough integration of the series of factors that gave birth to social conflict in Nigeria (Mason and Rychard, 2005).

METHODOLOGY

This work is historical in nature and thus used qualitative method to carry out the task of the research. Hence, the sources of data relying mainly on secondary source. Survey method

was also used for consistent approach of data collection from a subset of a phenomena. This allows for interpretation of the data and the creation of generalizations through secondary data across a large geographical area.

Existing literature on the topic of study such as textbooks, journals, magazines, government documents, conference papers, internet, and the work of some distinguished scholars among other related documents were among the primary sources consulted and carefully selected for the study. The author further consulted some public and private libraries within the country to collect data for the work.

The study therefore entailed a chronological and thematic presentation of the work in line with the historical method and due to the limitation of secondary data. The work systematically presents first-hand report. The result and discussion were carried out with the objectivity of mind in attempt to present an accurate information about the subject of the paper.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

- **Causes Of Social Conflict in Nigeria**

Nigeria has remained a hotbed of constant upheavals and life-threatening social disorder that threaten peace, security and sustainable development of the nation. It is obvious that Nigeria has been in the clutches of various forms of social conflicts which persistently manifesting. The study identifies few of the salient causes of the social conflicts in Nigeria amongst:

➤ **Ethnic Identity:** The diversities that arise from ethnic differences among groups in Nigeria society has a link to violent social conflict. Ethnic variety increases the risk of violent social disputes in countries (Collier, 2001). The likelihood of social conflict is doubled when a dominant ethnic group exists. Further shutting out certain ethnic groups from political process may exacerbate ethnic tensions (Adedeji, 2025). Lijphardt (1999) cited in Itumo, Udeuhele and Aro (2017) alleged that the majoritarian democratic systems' adversarial nature can exacerbate ethnic tensions and significantly raise the risk of social conflicts.

For the reason that resources and power are not allocated fairly, many Nigerians organize and align themselves along ethnic lines (Adedeji, 2023). Itumo et al. (2017) provided evidence to support this claim, that a large portion of the population considers themselves to be part of ancient ethnic, regional, and religious groupings. Disintegration, secession, civil struggle, civil war, minority agitation, and violent conflicts, of which all are typically regarded as abnormal to normal state formation are very common threats or actual occurrences in Nigeria's fragmented states (Osaghea and Suberu, 2005).

➤ **Religious Identity:** As a cause of societal conflict, religious identity comes in second only to ethnicity. Though more precarious than ethnic identification under the Fourth Republic, and it actually acts to energize ethnicity. In Nigeria, religious identities are typically divided into three categories: Christian, Muslim and traditional. Traditional religions are the least politically

active of the three. Essentially, religious struggle and divergence have been centered on Christian and Muslim identities. The structural challenges of the North been primarily Muslim and the South predominantly Christian of which the difference has been the root cause of the North-South cleft, which has widened ethnic divides in Nigeria.

➤ **Economic Motivation:** There is an economic component to the prevalence of violent conflicts in society. According to Kavanagh (2011), poverty among highly educated people may also be a determining factor in their participation in social conflict. She asserted that for individuals who were economically disadvantaged, a high degree of education was a far stronger predictor of participation in activist groups than for those who had access to capital. Honaker (2008) also revealed that unemployment in any society prompted a discernment of economic discrimination and could be a leading cause of violent social conflict.

The implication of the above submission is that poverty may serve as a suitable variable in determining the formation of activist groups which may propel social conflict. Hence, it can therefore be averred that poverty has contributed immensely to social conflict in Nigeria. Furthermore, Blomberg and Hess (2002) discovered that the emergence of social conflicts is significantly predicted by the severe economic conditions brought on by economic crisis. Overwhelming debt obligations, however, adversely affect

Nigeria government ability to deliver the dividends of good governance and this invariably resulted to social conflict. The enormous debt burdens afflicting Nigeria, compounded by ineffectiveness of government has often inflame tensions.

- **Relative Deprivation:** In the line of agreement with Gurr (2006), people may be more likely to participate in social unrest, if members of their group or another group are denied something they feel they are entitled to. When a group of people compare their positions in society to others, and realise they have less than they should, can incite the group to violence as an attempt to seek redress for the relative deprivation of their social group or others. The case of Niger Delta fits this scenario. Due to shared frustration of different groups toward a regime, people with divergent interests may work together by creating tension around the country in order to see their expectations met. In line with Brass (2003), many in Nigeria have participated in violence conflict because they believe so strongly in the need to redress deprivation meted out to them.
- **Incompetent Governance:** This is improper management and execution of government functions. It can also be referred to as inability of a government to deliver the dividend of governance to the citizens, hence a weak state. Due to the absent of a healthy state, a power vacuum is created, which inevitably gives resentful factions the chance to incite societal conflict. A number of mechanisms may be used by the aggrieved groups, including the ease of recruiting refugees and other marginalized groups, the terrorist

organization's ability to appeal to the public as a "surrogate state" that provides institutions and services, the connection between the success of terrorist groups and civil or communal discord, and the use of transnational terrorist organizations as surrogates for other states to attract the attention of the target state and the international community as a social movement (Atzili, 2010).

- **Diversionsary Use of Force:** Deceptive use of force has the potential to cause societal unrest and undermine a polity's democratic consolidation. There is evidence that the lack of political freedom and access also aid the perpetration of social conflict. Violent resistance becomes more appealing when political channels for change is inaccessible. Dassel and Reinhardt (1999) posit that social conflict can turn violence when government reacts forcefully to protests that arise from contested national issues. Repression has become one of major responses of Nigeria government to citizens' demand. Reactions from citizens have always been to counter the repressive action through violence approach. Clamping down on civil resistance in Nigeria has always given birth to violent social conflict in an attempt to be efficacious.

- **Military in Government:** It has long been claimed that the military's involvement in governance makes society more susceptible to violent social unrest. According to Itumo et al. (2017), the protracted years of military administration were a contributing factor in

the violent conflicts witnessed in Nigeria (Agbaje and Ohonvbere, 2000). They further argued that it has caused Nigerian society to become more militarized and that several armed organizations have emerged as a result, such the Bakasi Boys in the South-East, the O’Odua Peoples’ Congress (OPC) in the South-West, the Arewa Peoples’ Congress (APC) in the North, and the Egbesu Boys of Africa in the Niger Delta. Out of fifty-four years of Nigeria independence, military had spent a total of thirty years in the governance of the country, during which time its political and social ideals were severely damaged.

- **Effects of Social Conflict on Sustainable Development of Nigeria Nation**

There are identified effects of social conflicts on sustainable development of Nigeria nation. Few of these are highlighted below.

- **Political Instability:** Social conflict has led to political instability and negative consequences in the country. The Civil War also referred to as Biafra War led to loss of lives and properties (Madiebo, 1984). The aftermath of the war has damaged the relationship among various ethnic groups in Nigeria (Adedeji, 2025). Political instability as a product of conflict signifies unconducive atmosphere for taking and implementing progressive decision and distraction between people and the leadership by pursuing selfish ambitions, discontinuity in policies and programmes. All these have successfully hindered the attainment of social-economic advancement for the country.

- **Disruption of Education Programme:** In any program aimed at sustainable development, education is essential. The country is working to improve the quality of education in the nation by installing facilities. However, this is made more difficult by the constant shutdown of educational institutions when conflict breaks out and intensifies. Many schools were forced to close down for months purposely because of incessant atrocity committed as a result of social conflict. Imam (2004) opined that education of innocent youths were disrupted by this tumultuous situation created by social conflict, as many were forced to emigrate from the crises area.

- **Danger to National Security:** National security has been gravely threatened by violent societal conflicts. Nigeria has actually been fortunate not to have been threatened by any external assault; otherwise, she may have broken up since and ceased to exist as a country. However, Nigeria is presently experiencing internal insecurity. It is crucial to consider Nwolise (1985) as depicted:

"A nation may possess the best police force, customs officers, secret service agents, best prisons, and the best armed forces in terms of training and equipment, but it may still be the most insecure country in the world due to poor governance, a population that is alienated and suffering, ignorance, hunger, and unemployment."

Therefore, a society that experiences social inequality, economic hardship, political injustice, religious or ethnic hostility, human rights abuses, etc., is extremely unstable (Nwolise, 1985).

- **Increase in the Rate of Unemployment:** Social conflict increases gross rate of unemployment in the country. One of the main causes of concern is the unemployment rate, especially among young people. Many young people in the nation plagued by social unrest were not just unemployed, but also denied access to economic empowerment and education (Aremu, 2010). If there is no economic support from the government or society, there is a tendency for unemployed former militants to participate in illicit activities like dealing in the circulation of small guns.
- **Loss of Lives:** Numerous violent social conflicts in Nigeria have claimed the lives of a large number of Nigerians. It is regrettable to observe that Nigeria's human resources are being severely impacted by the country's record-breaking death toll from violence conflicts. The departed soul's excellent abilities, skills, and potential are no longer available to be used for the sustainable development of the country.
- **Negative Impact on Economic Development:** The nation's economic growth is negatively impacted by the persistent violent social unrest. According to Adebayo (2010), the nation's revenue source is similarly impacted by the crisis, in addition to the

fact that many of the country's virile men suffer grave consequences that ultimately result in their deaths. Almost every action done to control the problem is not beneficial to the economy. Curfews, for instance, make it difficult to move freely from one location to another, which stops all economic activity. It follows that crises are a hindrance to economic sustainability since no economic growth could occur in a climate of chaos, fear, and uncertainty.

- **Increase in Poverty Rate:** To compliment the above, conflict in Nigeria has also hurt the nation's economic fortunes thereby giving birth to poverty of highest level. Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has significantly declined as a result of the political impasse and sporadic outbursts of violence. The current inability to increase investment rates has resulted in low GDP growth rates for a number of years, ranging between 3% and 4%, compared to the 7% needed yearly to accomplish the Millennium Development Goals (poverty reduction). This, also manifested in individual standard of living. More than 70% of Nigeria is living below poverty line. This affected mostly those displaced by conflicts, those who lost their bread winner, and those who lost their properties or source of their income.

➤ **Proliferation of Small Arms and Light Weapons:** Incessant social uprising in Nigeria has put the country in a security risk. Due to social injustice and deprivation syndrome, various militia groups employed violence through the availability of weapons to demand for justice (Ujomu, 2002). The question is what happens to these weapons at the end of the operation? Some of the arms will be sold to migrants and criminals who will eventually use them for robbery in the country (Akinwunmi 2008). These weapons can also aggravate minor disputes to the level of war purposely because of easy access to weapons.

➤ **Backward Movement:** Adebayo (2010) asserted that no noteworthy advancement could be documented in a Build, Destroy, and Rebuild (BDR) environment since it equates to a circle of cycling. Essentially, it cost the government billions of naira to install varieties of facilities that had been destroyed during societal unrest. Restructuring and repairing what was harmed during the crisis would require resources that could have been used to start other developmental initiatives and upgrade the amenities. The government typically compensated victims of crises, squandering millions of naira that could have been allocated to other programs for growth.

- **Envisioning Social Justice in Managing Social Conflict in Nigeria**

Social conflicts arise out of clashes of interests or problems from incompatibility of interests, and have lately assumed a much more precarious form in Nigeria. These conflicts have been vicious as personal interests have overshadowed the common interests and the dictate of official responsibility is been negatively affected. The situation has always led to contention seen in the prevalence of violence.

Several groups have been subjected to untold pain, suffering and have become voiceless in the determination of those critical issues affecting them (Committee on Defence of Human Rights, 2000b). There has been demand from these different ethnic groups, religious groups, professional groups and social groups in Nigeria which are essentially for those social-political conditions which guarantee them peaceful cohabitation.

Given the fact that these demands have not been properly addressed, social conflict has therefore degenerated to the stage in which several groups have regularly engaged federal government. To address all these, social justice and equity must be the central focus. Adedeji (2025) maintained the need to recognise and face the challenge of managing Nigeria plural character to achieve the desire for a strong, stable and united nation.

The current character of social conflicts has been associated with Nigerian state and ruling elites carrying out oppression, deprivation and marginalisation against the

oppressed groups (Ujomu, 2002). Hence, social conflict has transcended the much touted and dichotomized struggles between the rulers and the ruled, the oppressors and the oppressed.

There is need to transformed any structure that served as root causes of social conflict in Nigeria. The dogmatic and rigidity approach will continue to inflate the conflict, as the belief that social conflicts are rigidly configured and hence cannot be transformed is a fiction. To cope with the crisis, there need to adopt systematic and sustainable approach. The approach of social justice initiative is fundamental.

According to Ujomu (2002), social justice is the foundational framework for the complete development of the human person in his or her physical, social, and spiritual life. Its main goal is to eradicate institutionalized oppression and domination. It is believed that social justice places a strong emphasis on the welfare and well-being of every member of society.

The means through which all sections of the society can arrive at some consensus to reconcile disparity in interests with one another is also necessary and embrace social justice. Hence, issues of justice are vital for the resolution of social conflicts as Mitchell (1996) cited in Ujomu (2002) maintained that:

- ❖ A conflict at any level in society usually involves a struggle for justice;
- ❖ Justice is the question of what constitutes a proper social order that can lead to human flourishing.

- ❖ Justice is the unwavering commitment to give every man his due;
- ❖ Society that committed to social justice will prosper than the one who lacks the practices;
- ❖ Justice is the regard one has for other people's freedom;
- ❖ Justice permits all persons to participate freely and equally in issues that regulate their conduct; etc.

For peace, order and stability in Nigeria society, social justice needs to be upheld. The degree to which a society will ensure the survival and well-being of its members depends on how consistently and resolutely it pursues peace. The central aim of conflict resolution should be to establish enduring peace and justice for those concerned. There are several means of resolving conflict; however, one of the most effective means is by establishing an effective system of social justice.

CONCLUSION

The effect of social conflict on the present-day Nigeria is worrisome, and hence needs immediate attention. The study has proven that despite Nigeria been the giant and pride of Africa and the one of the epicenters of human civilization with abundant potential of becoming great still bedevilled with unfathomable social conflicts which have harmfully dealt with its sustainable development. Social conflict in Nigeria embedded in the past events and the pluralistic background of the Nigerian state.

The adopted multicausal theory of the study upheld that social conflict in Nigeria is multidimensional which may be viewed from

structural, political, cultural, religious, geographical and sociological angles closely attributed to the problem of social injustice. The study concluded that the problem of social conflict in Nigeria multifaceted putting question of security along with survival of Nigeria on the center stage. The peace of the country will remain weaken and permanently erode its sustainable development unless the question of social injustice is holistically addressed by all and sundry knowing fully well that only quasi development could be accomplished in an atmosphere of crisis

- **Recommendations**

Having extensively carried out the study, the following were recommended for action:

- (1) **Plurality and ethnicity should be positively construed.** The strength in diversity should be the goal of all ethnic groups instead of using it as a bases of unhealthy rivalries. Due to ethnic pluralistic nature of Nigeria, proportional representation system should be embraced rather than adversarial majoritarian electoral system that has the potential to inflame ethnic tensions.
- (2) **Religion is a belief system and an attempt to worship the Sacred God in an identified and accepted ways.** Religion teaches moral, and hence the adherents coupled with the government should practice it accordingly without mixing it with politics. As Nigeria is a secular state, citizens should be allowed to choose and practice the religion of his/her conviction. Government should also

stop parading any of the faith as a state religion.

- (3) **Social welfare policies such as social security, employment, health and education should be strengthened.** Spending on social welfare will automatically reduce poverty, inequality, and socioeconomic insecurity, and hence discourage engagement in violence social conflict.
- (4) **The doctrine of social justice should be enshrined into Nigeria system.** Hence, elimination of institution of domination and oppression is sacrosanct. In this, the dues of every individual and group should be given accordingly with objectivity
- (5) **Good governance is sacrosanct to reduce the social conflict in Nigeria.** Proper management and execution of government functions by competent administration, and appropriately and adequately delivery of the dividend of governance to the citizens is key. This will give birth to a strong state which will discourage promotion of social conflict.
- (6) **The use of force to address agitation should be discouraged.** It should be registered in the mind of government that violence cannot quench violence but peace. Political freedom and discussion with involvement of all stakeholders should be encouraged. Government should prioritise peace and participation rather than repression.

(7) **Military intervention in governance should be discouraged with all unity of purpose.** The prolonged years of military in Nigeria has done more harms than good. The citizens who have been militarized through military psyche should be counseled to embrace civility.

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